

1 **The influence of temperature and vapour pressure deficit on conidia germination and germ tube production in**
2 **an Australian *Podosphaera xanthii* isolate.**

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15 **Abstract**

16 Powdery mildew of cucurbits, caused by *Podosphaera xanthii*, is an economic constraint in cucurbit production
17 worldwide. This study examined the influence of temperature and vapour pressure deficit (VPD) on the rate of conidial
18 germination and the formation of germ tubes in an Australian *P. xanthii* isolate 12 – 48 hours after inoculation. Two
19 experiments were prepared by inoculating cucumber, cv. crystal salad, leaf-discs using a spore settling tower. The first
20 experiment incubated inoculated cucumber leaf-discs at eight temperatures between 8 and 35°C under saturated
21 vapour pressure (SVP), the second compared 18 VPD conditions between 0.038 and 1.797 kPa, in six humidity
22 chambers (33% – 99% relative humidity) and three temperatures (22°C, 25°C, 28°C). Leaf-discs were cleared, stained
23 and microscopically inspected for conidial germination and the number of germ tubes. The optimal temperature for
24 germination was 28°C at SVP, where more than 50% of conidia had germinated by 12 hours, and 85% by 48 hours.
25 Fewer germinated conidia were recorded after 12 hours at other temperature treatments between 17°C and 31°C. The
26 germination percentage and germination rate was significantly lower when vapour pressure was between 0.13 and 2.5
27 kPa, with germination in response to VPD varying by approximately 10%, indicating difficulty associating conidial
28 germination to VPD above 0.13 kPa. Germ tubes production was highest between 25 °C and 28 °C at the lowest VPD
29 treatment at near SVP, with more than 50% of the germinated conidia producing at least three germ tubes. Germination
30 and formation of germ tubes significantly reduced when VPD increased. *P. xanthii* conidia were able to produce a
31 primary germ tube under relatively dry conditions, such as 2.53kPa, but these results show infection would be less
32 likely and require longer incubation. This study provides the first crucial step in simulating powdery mildew infections
33 on cucurbit plants and may lead to a model capable of providing risk forecasts or fungicide management decision
34 support tools.

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36 **Additional keywords:** cucurbit, powdery mildew, *Podosphaera xanthii*, conidial germination, germ tube formation,
37 vapour pressure deficit, temperature, disease risk modelling.

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41 **Introduction**

42 Powdery mildew, caused by *Podosphaera xanthii* (Castagne) U. Braun & Shishkoff, is a constraint for cucurbit
43 production worldwide. The disease causes quantitative and qualitative yield losses impacting the economic return to
44 growers (Sapak et al. 2017).

45 Inoculum for primary infection by *P. xanthii* occurs from wind dispersed ascospores, produced by cleistothecia
46 following sexual recombination, or asexual conidia produced on a wide range of alternative hosts. In Australia reports
47 of sexually compatible strains of *P. xanthii* are uncommon (Letham and Priest 1989; Parbery 1990) and the co-
48 occurrence of two compatible mating types in the field is rare. In addition, primary infection by ascospores on some
49 cucurbit species may not be possible (McGrath 1994; Smith 1970) making their role in causing the disease unclear.
50 Due to a wide potential host range and lack of detail for which pathogen isolates are capable of infecting alternative
51 hosts, it seems researchers are currently resigned to the assumption that *P. xanthii* conidial inoculum is ubiquitous.

52 High conidial germination rates on a susceptible host can result in greater powdery mildew severity if environmental
53 conditions are also conducive for colonisation and sporulation (Jarvis et al. 2002; Trecate et al. 2019). Temperature
54 and relative humidity (RH) are cited as the two most influential environmental variables in powdery mildew epidemics
55 (Jarvis et al. 2002; Sitterly 1978; Suleiman et al. 2016). Other variables such as air turbulence, light radiation and the
56 structural and chemical properties of the host leaf have also shown to influence infections (Itagaki and Shibuya 2018;
57 Yarwood 1957).

58 The asexual lifecycle can be simplified into the following stages; germination, germ tube elongation, germ tube
59 branching, infection, colonization, candle production, and dispersal (Jarvis et al. 2002). Following germ tube initiation
60 and elongation, appressoria form in attempt to pierce the host epidermal cells with a penetration peg. Successful
61 penetration of the host cell wall by the pathogen leads to the formation of haustoria, which it uses to obtain nutrients
62 while extending its mycelial mass over the leaf surface (Green et al. 2002). Haustoria are often difficult to observe
63 using microscopy and therefore observations of germinated conidia with secondary germ tubes as indicators of
64 successful infection are used as a proxy for successful parasitism (Trecate et al. 2019). The time between germination
65 and appressoria development can occur rapidly in powdery mildews. Nair (1962) described *E. graminis* producing

66 appressoria within 4 hours of conidia germination, followed by successful penetration of the wheat host 6 – 8 hours
67 later. It is the time between conidia germination and colonisation when RH or vapour pressure deficit (VPD) is
68 suspected to have the greatest influence on successful infection (Aust and Hoyningen-Huene 1986; Reuveni and
69 Rotem 1974; Yarwood 1957). The survivability of conidia has been reviewed as highly variable between species and
70 isolates (Yarwood et al. 1954). The conidia of some powdery mildew species survive longer in humid environments,
71 while other species in drier environments, showing that specific host and pathogen studies are needed to understand
72 disease infection and establishment (Nagy 1976).

73 Relative humidity (RH) is the percentage of water held in the air (e_a) relative to the potential water holding capacity
74 at saturation (e_s). Vapour pressure deficit (VPD) is calculated as the difference between the actual atmospheric vapour
75 pressure (e_a) and the vapour pressure at saturation (e_s). Both measurements are determined by temperature, which
76 defines e_s (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. 2020). VPD is described as a more appropriate
77 variable, compared to relative humidity, in host-parasite studies as it has a better linear correlation with
78 evapotranspiration compared to RH which is non-linear (Anderson 1936; Jarvis et al. 2002). For ease, hereafter we
79 will use VPD in place of references to RH, unless where the specific use of RH is necessary.

80 Studies have reported that powdery mildew conidia germinate in a higher proportion when vapour pressures are at, or
81 very near saturation, and when saturated conditions are prolonged, especially in the first 24 hours (Jarvis et al. 2002;
82 Reuveni and Rotem 1974; Trecate et al. 2019; Yarwood 1957). However, some studies have reported no difference
83 between moisture treatments, these tend to be studies which have not included saturated vapour pressure (e_s)
84 conditions, or make the first observation of germinating conidia after 24 hours (Hural 1986; Jarvis et al. 2002; Xu and
85 Butt 1998). For example, in vitro germination studies by Hashioka (1937) and Cheah et al. (1996) reported no conidial
86 germination on glass slides at RH of < 99% and < 94% respectively, while Reuveni and Rotem (1974) observed low
87 germination at RH conditions 50-55% and the highest germination at 80 – 85% with prolonged leaf moisture (up to
88 24 hours).

89 Following the successful infection and development of a haustorium, usually after 24 hours (Trecate et al. 2019),
90 differences in VPD, were observed to not influence powdery mildew colony growth and the subsequent production of
91 conidiophores (Grove and Boal 1991; Jarvis et al. 2002; Nagy 1976; Yarwood 1957).

92 The influence of temperature on the germination of powdery mildew conidia and its subsequent development is less
93 controversial in the literature compared to VPD, and the differences between conidial germination in many cases can
94 be attributed to the specific pathogenic strain and host interaction (Nagy 1976; Yarwood et al. 1954). In cucurbit hosts,
95 temperature optimums for conidial germination range between 25- 28°C (Cheah et al. 1996; Hashioka 1937; Reuveni
96 and Rotem 1974; Trecate et al. 2019). However, *P. xanthii* isolates found in Queensland, Australia, may have broader
97 preferences for temperature and humidity between 10-35°C (MacManus and Akem 2008; Sapak et al. 2017). Prior
98 studies investigating the impact of VPD on infection and the establishment of powdery mildew have aided a granular
99 understanding of their role during infection. In order to calibrate the Powdery Mildew of Cucurbits Simulation
100 (POMICS) model (Sapak et al. 2017) for the impact of VPD and temperature on disease establishment a finer scale of
101 environmental variables need to be studied.

102 Detailed infection studies of *P. xanthii* collected from Queensland, or elsewhere in Australia, have yet to report ideal
103 conditions for powdery mildew epidemics. Therefore we undertook infection studies on a local cucurbit powdery
104 mildew isolate in controlled environment facilities to understand the influence of temperature and VPD on the rate of
105 disease establishment by observing the success of conidial germination and germ tube production in the first 48 hours
106 of infection. The results from this work will inform the POMICS model that can be used by cucurbit growers and
107 agronomists as a decision support tool to manage the disease.

108

109 **Materials and Methods**

110 **Source of leaf-discs and inoculum:** Infection experiments were undertaken on seedlings of susceptible cucumber
111 variety ‘Crystal Salad’ (Terranova Seed Pty Ltd, NSW Australia) grown to a 2 - 3 true leaf stage in free draining pots,
112 9 cm in diameter under ambient glasshouse conditions at The University of Queensland Gatton Campus. A wild-type
113 *P. xanthii* isolate was sampled from the Queensland Department of Agriculture and Fisheries research station Gatton
114 during 2008 and serially passaged on cucumber ‘Crystal Salad’ plants in a separate glasshouse to generate a continuous
115 source of *P. xanthii* inoculum. The growth media comprised of 1 cubic meter 0-10 mm composted bark (Basset Barks,
116 Sunshine Coast, QLD) mixed thoroughly with 2 kg / m³ Osmocote Plus (8-9 months release, Scotts Australia Pty Ltd,
117 NSW), 1 kg Osmocote Plus (3 – 4 months release), 1.2 kg MoisturAid granular wetting agent (Yates Australia, NSW),

118 1.2 kg Dolomite (Mudgee Dolomite and Lime Pty Ltd, NSW), and 1.3 kg Osmoform 4-month release (Scotts Australia
119 Pty Ltd, Australia). Seedlings were irrigated twice daily for 15 min using an automated drip system.

120 **Inoculation:** Cucumber leaves were sampled at dusk between 1800 – 1900 hours. Leaves sampled at this time of day
121 have higher carbohydrate levels than those collected earlier (Figure 1a) and thus considered more suitable for use in
122 the leaf-disc based studies (Amand and Wehner 1995; Yarwood 1946). Two fully expanded leaves from 4-week-old
123 plants were excised in the laboratory at room temperature ($22 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$), rinsed with sterile distilled water to remove dirt
124 and unwanted particles, then gently dried on filter paper. Once dried, the leaf-discs (22 mm diameter) were excised
125 using a cork borer, then placed adaxial side up on sponge inserts soaked with sterile distilled water within 30 mL
126 McCartney bottles (Figure 1b). The leaf-discs were secured in place beneath caps modified to have a 20 mm diameter
127 hole, exposing the adaxial leaf-disc surface (Figure 1c). Once secured, the leaf-discs were placed at the bottom of a
128 spore settling tower and inoculated in groups of 12. The spore settling tower was constructed from a flanged Perspex
129 cylinder (100cm in height, 40 cm diameter, and 20 mm thick). For each inoculation run fifteen infested cucumber leaf-
130 discs 22 mm in diameter were placed on a platform suspended at the top of the spore settling tower below the air inlet
131 valve. Conidia were dislodged from the infested leaves by first slowly applying a vacuum of -20 kPa to the spore
132 settling tower, then sharply breaking the seal to produce a consistent rush of air across the infested leaf surface. The
133 dispersed conidia were left to settle on the exposed leaf-discs, mounted in McCartney bottles, placed on the base plate
134 of the settling tower. Conidial density on the leaf-disc surface was estimated by applying Stoke's law of sedimentation
135 as suggested by Reifschneider and Boiteux (1988). Stoke's Law of sedimentation predicts the settling velocity and
136 unit density of smooth spheres with diameters between about 1 and 70 μm . This method achieved a suitably even
137 distribution of *P. xanthii* conidia which have a size of 24 –28 x 58-72 μm . A subset of four leaf-discs were assessed
138 immediately following inoculation to confirm the estimated spore densities were consistent between inoculation
139 replicates and that no pre-germinated conidia were introduced to the leaf-discs at inoculation.

140 Temperature and VPD controlled experiments were undertaken using 5 L airtight plastic containers containing 500
141 mL distilled water or saturated salt solutions to achieve the targeted humidity levels (Table 1) (Winston and Bates
142 1960). SVP and VPD were calculated using equations 1 and 2 described by Murray (1967). A miniature (4-cm
143 diameter; 12 V) fan attached to the underside of the lid circulated air to ensure uniform temperature and VPD
144 conditions. The humidity chambers were placed in an illuminated constant-temperature incubator (Astra Panels

145 Salisbury, Brisbane, Australia) in a completely randomised layout. Calibrated temperature and humidity sensors
146 (Monitor Sensors Pty. Ltd., Caboolture, Australia) logged conditions in the chambers every 15 minutes and three
147 GroLux® growth fluorescent tubes (Osram Sylvania®, Australia) were programmed to emit a light intensity of 2.0
148 $\text{Wm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ at the leaf level on a 14 / 10 hour light-dark cycle.

149 **Effect of temperature on conidial germination and germ tube development at saturated VPD:** The effect of
150 temperature on conidial germination and germ tube production were compared in eight treatments, 8, 17, 19, 22, 25,
151 28, 31, and 35°C ($\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$) with a saturated target VPD of 0 kPa, which varied between 0.02 to 0.04 kPa. Conidial
152 germination of *P. xanthii* were assessed at 12, 24, 36, and 48 hours after inoculation, by randomly sampling two leaf-
153 discs from each humidity chamber. A similar number were sampled to assess germ tube development following leaf
154 clearing. The experiment was repeated once.

155 Conidial germination was observed by removing conidia from the leaf-disc surfaces using a 4 × 2 cm piece of adhesive
156 tape (Amsalem et al. 2006). The tape was then mounted on a glass slide over a drop of Lactophenol cotton blue stain.
157 Prepared slides were observed under an Olympus compound light microscope (40x) and 100 conidia were assessed
158 per leaf-disc. Conidia with a primary germ tube with a length of at least half the diameter of the conidia were
159 considered germinated (Lacy 1994). Germ tubes were classified as primary, secondary or tertiary according to their
160 relative length.

161 Germ tube formation was observed on cleared leaf-discs under a compound microscope (40x). The leaf-discs were
162 cleared following the method described in Liberato (2005), and mounted on glass slides with a drop of 85% lactic acid
163 under a coverslip. Leaf-discs inspected at time periods 12, 24 and 48 hours for germ tube formation were discarded
164 due to either insufficient germ tube formation (12 and 24 hours) or excessive hyphal growth (48 hours). At 36 hours,
165 for each leaf-disc, 100 conidia were randomly assessed by counting germ tubes. Four leaf-discs were assessed for
166 conidial density immediately following inoculation to confirm no pre-germinated conidia were introduced to the leaf-
167 discs at inoculation. This experiment was repeated once.

168

169 **Effect of VPD on conidial germination and germ tubes at three temperature regimes:** The influence of VPD on
170 conidial germination and germ tube production was evaluated at three temperatures of 22, 25, and 28°C $\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, and

171 four relative humidity values (Table 2). Each temperature and relative humidity treatment provided an independent
172 VPD treatment. Each VPD treatment chamber contained 20 leaf replicates. Four leaf replicates were sampled at 12,
173 24, 36 and 48 hours after inoculation to assess spore germination using the sticky-tape method. The remaining four
174 were sampled at 36 hours to assess germ tube formation in-situ following leaf clearing and staining (Liberato et al.
175 2005).

176

$$177 \quad SVP = 10^{\left(\frac{T \times 7.5}{T + 237.3} + 0.786\right)} \times 0.1 \quad (1)$$

$$178 \quad VPD = SVP \times (RH \div 100) - SVP \quad (2)$$

179

180 **Data analysis:** All data were analysed in R version 4.2.0 (R Core Team 2022). Germination experiments were
181 analysed with binomial generalized additive models (gam) using the R package `mgcv` (Wood 2017). Data from
182 temperature range experiments fit germination to infection period using a thin plate spline consisting of three knots,
183 and temperature using penalized cubic splines specifying shrinkage consisting of 6 knots. In the VPD germination
184 experiments the gam which best fit the data used a thin plate spline on infection period with 3 knots, temperature
185 treatment as a linear term and penalized cubic splines fit to VPD with 4 knots.

186 Ordinal logistic regression was used to estimate germ tube production in the temperature and VPD experiments. This
187 regression method was used because the response variable can be defined as an ordered classification of different
188 conidial germination states. Four levels were defined as: 0 = non-germinated conidia, 1 = germinated conidia with 1
189 germ tube, 2 = germinated conidia with two germ tubes; and 3 = germinated conidia with three or more germ tubes.
190 In the temperature range experiment, germ tube production was fit to temperature with a basis spline containing four
191 knots at 8, 23, 28 and 35°C. In the VPD range experiment, germ tube production fit a VPD predictor using a basis
192 spline with a knot at 0.5 kPa and two boundary knots, temperature and experimental rep were specified as linear
193 predictors. A complete description of statistical methods, code and results can be found at
194 https://paulmelloy.github.io/P_xanthii_titlepage.html.

195 The ordinal logistic regression can be described as follows,

196
$$\text{logit}(P(Y \leq j)) = \beta_{j0} - n_1 x_1 \dots - n_p x_p \quad (3)$$

197 Where Y is the ordinal response variable (germ tube number), with j categories (0, 1, 2, 3 germ tubes). β is a predictor
198 variable such as temperature, VPD or incubation time; n is a vector of coefficients with length p , and x is a vector of
199 predictor values.

200

201 **Results**

202 **Effect of temperature on conidial germination and germ tube formation at saturated VPD**

203 Microscopic observation of four inoculated leaf-discs immediately following inoculation confirmed, no pre-
204 germinated conidia were introduced to the leaf-discs, and conidial density ranged between 66 and 71 per cm². *P.*
205 *xanthii* conidia germinated between 17 - 31°C, with the highest germination percentage at 28°C across all sampling
206 periods (Figure 2). No germination was observed in temperature treatments 8°C and 35°C at any time points. Despite
207 a significant interaction between temperature and incubation time ($P < 0.001$), the best fitting model showed
208 temperature ($P < 0.001$) and infection time ($P < 0.001$) as non-linear additive effects. The temperature germination
209 model estimated optimal conidial germination between 27°C and 28°C with an R^2 of 0.971 and Akaike information
210 criterion (AIC) value of 560.5. The data showed ~ 50% of conidia produced germ tubes within 12 hours of inoculation.
211 This proportion increased by another 10% 24 hours after inoculation and reached 85% at 48 hours. Germination at
212 temperatures between 22°C and 25°C (Figure 2) were on average slower than the 28°C treatment; after 24 hours
213 approximately 48% and 52% of the conidia germinated respectively, and approximately 75% to 80% germinated after
214 48 hours. Germination was significantly slower at temperatures lower than 22°C or greater than 29°C regardless of
215 incubation times. At 17°C, <10% of conidia had germinated after 12 hours, and only 25% had germinated after 48
216 hours (Figure 2).

217 Observations of the cleared leaf-discs with a microscope after 36 hours of incubation revealed that temperature had a
218 significant effect on germ tube production ($P < 0.001$) (Figure 3a). Tertiary germ tube production peaked between
219 25°C and 28°C, with a mean 49 - 53% of conidia producing at least three germ tubes respectively. Although there
220 were fewer conidia with tertiary germ tubes in the 22°C treatment, the proportion of secondary germ tubes were higher,

221 resulting in a mean 63% of conidia with two or more germ tubes in the 22, 25 and 28°C temperature treatments. An
222 ordinal logistic regression of germ tube production showed significant differences between temperature treatments (P
223 > 0.001) (Figure 3b). Only 4.5% of germinated conidia had produced tertiary germ tubes at 19°C, with no tertiary
224 germ tubes observed at 17°C and 31°C. Observations made during germ tube assessments noted the 25 - 28°C
225 treatments contained more primary and secondary germ tubes with elongated hyphae. These elongated hyphae also
226 established multiple penetration sites in the host tissues via appressoria along their hyphae. In comparison, 19°C and
227 31°C treatments showed primary and secondary germ tubes were consistently shorter after 36 hours of incubation.

228

229 **Effect of VPD on conidial germination and germ tube formation at three temperatures:** VPD had a significant
230 non-linear effect on *P. xanthii* conidia germination ($P < 0.001$). The best fit gam model ($R^2 = 0.958$) included a non-
231 linear term for incubation time ($P < 0.001$) and a linear term across the three temperatures ($P < 0.001$). The highest
232 conidial germination was obtained at VPD values close to saturation (0.026 kPa) at the three tested temperatures,
233 22°C, 25°C and 28°C (Figure 4). Germination significantly dropped when the VPD increased, irrespective of the
234 temperature or incubation time. A gam model testing the interaction between VPD and temperature, while significant,
235 was not a better fit than a model without interaction between variables VPD, temperature and infection period.
236 Germination seemed to be less affected by VPD in treatments over 0.5 kPa, and these drier treatments may have been
237 more affected by temperature. The warmer treatments of 25°C and 28°C, showed a slight rise in conidial germination
238 between 1.5 and 2 kPa after 24 hours (Figure 4).

239 VPD also had a significant effect on the development of germ tubes ($P < 0.001$). Germinated conidia with tertiary
240 germ tubes were most prevalent in the lowest VPD treatments, with the warmer treatments producing a greater
241 proportion of tertiary germ tubes ($P = 0.001$) (Figure 5a). Differences between the repeated experiments were
242 significant ($P < 0.001$) yet the three experimental replicates showed similar trends.

243 As in the germination experiments, drier treatments with a VPD greater than 0.038 kPa showed significantly fewer
244 germinated conidia (Figure 5a). Of the germinated conidia in the VPD treatments 0.132 kPa or greater, conidia with
245 a single germ tube were in a higher proportion than conidia with secondary or tertiary germ tubes. Secondary germ
246 tubes were produced in all VPD treatments, although the percentage of conidia producing secondary germ tubes

247 reduced significantly in drier VPD treatments equal to or greater than 0.132 kPa. While very few tertiary germ tubes
248 were observed in the driest VPD treatment (2.57 kPa), the pathogen was able to produce secondary germ tubes and
249 tertiary germ tubes in all treatments (Figure 5a). The presence of appressoria were still seen after 36 hours of incubation
250 at 22°C and 0.66 kPa (Figure 6).

251 Cleared leaf-discs from the $28 \pm 2^\circ\text{C} / 0.038 \text{ kPa}$ treatment showed some *P. xanthii* conidia produced forked primary
252 germ tube after 12 hours of incubation. A secondary germ tube would then emerge after 24 hours from another part
253 of the conidium. This secondary germ tube then elongated, with the attendant development of appressoria. The
254 appressoria of *P. xanthii* developed without a specific shape, unlike other powdery mildew species, but hyphal
255 widening could be used to differentiate the appressoria from the hyphae, as suggested by (Boesewinkel 1977). From
256 beneath the appressoria, penetration pegs developed and pierced the epidermal host cells. These infection structures
257 could be observed after 24 hours on cleared leaf tissues (Figure 5). Once a parasitic relationship was established with
258 the host, conidia were able to produce more germ tubes and branching hyphae, as observed after 36 and 48 hours of
259 incubation.

260

261 **Discussion**

262 This study found temperature and VPD play significant roles in the germination rate and production of secondary and
263 tertiary *P. xanthii* germ tubes on cucurbit leaves. Moderate temperatures of 22– 28°C and a low VPD near saturation
264 provided the optimal conditions for successful infection and are likely to accelerate powdery mildew infection and
265 development early in the asexual lifecycle.

266 These optimal (22– 28°C), maximum ($\leq 31^\circ\text{C}$) and minimum ($> 8^\circ\text{C}$) germination temperatures are complimentary
267 to earlier reports of *P. xanthii* on cucurbits (Cheah et al. 1996; Gupta et al. 2001; Hashioka 1937; Trecate et al. 2019).
268 For example, Hashioka (1937) and Trecate et al. (2019) both reported suppressed germination below 10°C on cucurbit
269 leaves, and no germination below 5°C (Hashioka 1937). Studies reporting *P. xanthii* germination on glass slides,
270 however, observed much higher minimum germination temperatures with either a trace amount, or no germinating
271 conidia below 15 - 18°C (Cheah et al. 1996; Hashioka 1937; Nagy 1976). This might be due to the VPD on the

272 phylloplane likely being lower and more conducive for germination and/or the pathogen responding to the presence
273 of the host.

274 Excessive temperatures of 35°C prevented *P. xanthii* conidia germinating in this study. These observations, under
275 saturated conditions, again corroborated studies by Hashioka (1937) and Trecate et al. (2019) where almost no
276 germination was observed at 34°C and > 35°C respectively. These similar temperature optimums and ranges are
277 surprising considering the differences in experimental design and spatial populations from where the pathogen was
278 sampled in each study (Australia, Taiwan and the Czech Republic). These findings reinforce how uncontroversial the
279 temperature response of *P. xanthii* infecting cucurbits under saturated vapour pressure are among researchers. The
280 moisture requirements reported for *P. xanthii* germination and germ tube production on a cucurbit host, however, are
281 often reported with less consistency between studies.

282 VPD played an important role in the speed at which *P. xanthii* conidia germinated and produced germ tubes in this
283 study. VPD treatments which were close to saturated (0.04 - 0.2 kPa), showed significantly higher rates of conidial
284 germination and germ tube production in the three temperature treatments tested (22, 25, 28°C). These findings largely
285 support other studies where moisture treatments close to saturation increased germination, infection and conidia
286 survival in cucurbits (Cheah et al. 1996; Hashioka 1937; Reuveni and Rotem 1974).

287 In this study the differences between germination and production of secondary and tertiary germ tubes in the two most
288 saturated treatments (0.026 and 0.132 kPa; or 99 and 95% RH) at 22°C were on average 36%. However, Hashioka
289 (1937) reported minimal differences in conidial germination between their 100% and 94 - 97% RH treatments
290 (temperature range 11 – 13°C) after 1, 2, 4 and 6 days of incubation on cucurbit leaves. A comparison of these results
291 may seem conflicting if RH is not converted to VPD, as the lower temperature reduces the dryness of the air or VPD.
292 Hashioka's humidity treatments, 94 - 97% RH at 11 – 13°C equate to a VPD range of 0.04 – 0.09 kPa. Another
293 explanation for this difference might be the cooler temperatures in Hashioka's (1937) experiment aided in preserving
294 the conidia, however, we contend it might be more likely a combination of the lower temperatures and VPD.

295 This study is the first to clearly define the role of VPD influencing the germination and infection processes of *P.*
296 *xanthii*, thereby clarifying the observations made by previous authors on the influence of relative humidity on cucurbit
297 powdery mildews. Dry conditions were unable to prevent infection, since a small proportion of conidia were able to

298 survive at high VPD conditions without the presence of free water. These results support those reported by Reuveni
299 and Rotem (1974) and Hashioka (1937). The ability of some powdery mildew species to initiate the early formation
300 of germ tubes under low relative humidity has also been discussed by Yarwood (1950) , who suggested that species,
301 such as *P. xanthii* (Syn. *Sphaerotheca fuliginea*), have more internal liquid in their vacuole to initiate germination
302 under dry conditions without the presence of free water, which is required by other fungi for germination. In contrast,
303 a study by Sivapalan (1994) showed free water could displace conidia before infection and cause abnormally
304 germinating conidia unable to infect the host. Hashioka (1937) also noted similar observations of elongated germ tube
305 growth in water droplets which alter its ability to infect the host.

306 The results presented in this study show lower VPD resulted in greater infection but only describes half of the lifecycle.
307 For rapid powdery mildew onset and increased severity, multiple infection cycles are required. Reuveni and Rotem
308 (1974) show colonisation and dispersal of *P. xanthii* (Syn. *Sphaerotheca fuliginea*) conidia on squash leaves is
309 negatively affected by humidity. If the optimum conditions for both infection and sporulation stages are ignored, such
310 as reported by Whipps and Budge (2000) who maintained a constant relative humidity and temperature for eight weeks
311 to evaluate powdery mildew (*Oidium lycopersici*) disease severity on tomato plants, a different conclusion might be
312 reached to the optimum conditions for disease. Whipps and Budge (2000) thus concluded the optimum conditions for
313 powdery mildew establishment on tomatoes was approximately 80% RH (0.439 kPa VPD) and 19°C. Perhaps for
314 powdery mildew in cucurbits, like this experiment, if conditions were held constant for whole infection cycles,
315 including *P. xanthii* sporulation, a drier VPD optimum might be concluded. For plants in the field, however, the
316 pathogen is undoubtedly tuned to the diurnal fluctuations in temperature and humidity, where a drier daytime VPD
317 may facilitate pathogen sporulation and dispersal, while lower VPD and temperatures during the night preserve conidia
318 and encourage germination and infection. For plants grown in commercial temperature-controlled glasshouses,
319 however, these results are also highly relevant to managing powdery mildew. Periodic adjustment of air temperature
320 or VPD may disrupt the pathogen lifecycle, lowering the risk of disease and requirements for chemical control.

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322 In summary, the present study confirms the germination of *P. xanthii* conidia is constrained by temperature and VPD.
323 Low (< 8°C), high temperatures $\geq 35^{\circ}\text{C}$ and large VPD (> 0.2 kPa) provide less favourable conditions for pathogen
324 conidial germination and result in the reduction of disease risk (or severity) on cucurbits. In contrast, moderate
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325 temperatures between 22 and 28°C can enhance germination and formation of germ tubes which lead to infection
326 structures such as appressoria, penetration pegs and haustoria. This information can be used in developing a disease
327 model for powdery mildew of cucurbits. However, the influence of these two factors needs to be investigated under
328 field conditions with the impact of diurnal fluctuations in mind.

329

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336 **Compliance with ethical standards**

337 **Ethical statement**

338 This research did not involve any animal and/or human participants.

339 **Competing interests**

340 The authors declare that they have no conflict of interests.

341 **Data and code availability**

342 <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.21554712>

343 https://github.com/PaulMelloy/PM_cucurbit_infection

344 https://paulmelloy.github.io/P_xanthii_titlepage.html

345

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446 **Table 1.** Saturated salt solutions used to give different levels of relative humidity at each of five temperatures adapted
 447 from Winston and Bates (1960)

Saturated salt solution	Relative humidity (%)						
	10	15	20	25	28 [†]	30	35
Potassium hydrogen phosphate (KH ₂ PO ₄)	98.0	97.0	96.5	96.0	95.0	93.5	93.2 [†]
Potassium chloride (KCl)	88.0	86.5	85.0	85.0	85.0	84.5	83
Sodium chloride (NaCl)	76.0	76.0	76.0	75.5	75.5	75.5	75.5
Calcium nitrate (Ca(NO ₃) ₂ ·4H ₂ O)	57.5 [†]	56.0	55.5	50.5	50.0	47.0	43 [†]
Magnesium chloride (MgCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O)	34.0	34.0	33.0	32.5	32.5	32.5	32.5

448 [†] Approximated

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452 **Table 2.** Vapour pressure deficit and temperature treatments for assessing the portion of germinated conidia and
453 number of germ tubes.

Relative Humidity	Vapour Pressure Deficit at Three Temperatures		
	22°C	25°C	28°C
99 %	0.026	0.032	0.038
95 %	0.132	0.158	0.189
85 %	0.397	0.475	0.567
75 %	0.661	0.792	0.945
55 %	1.190	1.425	1.701
32 %	1.798	2.154	2.570

454 All VPD values given in units of kilopascals (kPa)

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463 **Figure 1.** Four-week-old cucumber seedlings cv. Crystal Salad used for the detached leaf method. (a) Two fully
464 expanded young cucumber leaves selected for leaf-disc harvest. (b) Side view of McCartney bottle, internal sponge
465 and cap and (c) top view of a leaf-disc exposed through opening in cap. (d) Incubation of inoculated cucumber leaf-
466 discs in humidity chambers placed in an illuminated constant temperature incubator.

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471 **Figure 2.** The effects of temperature on conidial germination at four incubation times. Each dot shows the
 472 raw observation data of the percentage germinated conidia from 100 conidia; the solid trend line shows the
 473 mean predicted model estimates, the dotted line indicates the 95% confidence intervals around the mean.

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477 **Figure 3.** (a) The mean *P. xanthii* germ tube formation as a percentage on cucumber leaf-discs at saturated
 478 atmospheric VPD values between approximately 0.02 kPa to 0.04 kPa at 36 hours after inoculation. (b) Ordinal
 479 logistic regression model of germ tubes production over a range of temperatures. Solid line indicates the estimated
 480 mean, the dotted line indicates the upper and lower 95% confidence interval around the mean. Temperature was
 481 fit to a b-spline with 4 knots.

482

483 **Figure 4.** The effects of atmospheric vapour pressure deficit (VPD) and temperature on conidial germination sampled
 484 after 12, 24, 36 and 48 hours of incubation. Points represent percentage germination observations of approximately
 485 100 conidia; solid trend lines show the mean germination percentage estimated by a generalized additive model.
 486 Dotted lines show the upper and lower 95% confidence intervals of each mean.

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490 **Figure 5.** (a) The effects of atmospheric vapour pressure deficit (VPD) at three different temperatures of 22°C,
 491 25°C and 28°C on formation of *P. xanthii* germ tubes on cucumber leaf-discs after 36 hours of incubation. (b)
 492 Predicted mean germ tube production over a range of VPD values, and the 95% confidence intervals. Values were
 493 predicted using an ordinal logistic regression model, VPD was fit to a b-spline with 3 knots, the middle knot set to
 494 0.5 kPa.

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504 **Figure 6.** Micrographs showing that germinated conidia stained with Lactophenol Cotton Blue at
505 approximately 0.60 kPa vapour pressure deficit produce at least three germ tubes, with the presence of
506 appressoria (indicated by black arrows) seen after 36 hours of incubation at 22°C. The primary germ tube
507 can be identified by the fork-shaped structure (indicated by the red arrow). The tertiary germ tube is
508 normally shorter than the secondary germ tube. The appressoria of *P. xanthii* develop without forming any
509 special shapes but can be recognized by a widening of the hyphae.

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